

Harmonised European Solutions for Testing Automation Road Transport

D2.2 Extension of the Common Methodology for the HEADSTART Key Enabling Technologies

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List of abbreviations and acronyms

The table herein presents the typical abbreviations used in WP2 – Test, validation and certification methodologies and procedures:

Abbreviation	Meaning
AD	Autonomous Driving
ADAS	Advanced Driver-Assistance System
C-V2X	Cellular Vehicle to Everything
CA	Certificate Authority
CAD	Connected Autonomous Driving
CAN	Controlled Area Network
CRL	Certificate Revocation List
CSMA/CA	Carrier-Sense Multiple Access with Collision Avoidance
DoA	Direction of Arrival
DoP	Dilution of Precision
DoS	Denial of Service
DuT	Device under Test
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
KETs	Key Enabling Technologies
IMU	Inertial Measurement Unit
I2V	Infrastructure to Vehicle
ITS	Intelligent Transportation System
LoS	Line of Sight
NTP	Network Time Protocol
NTRIP	Networked Transport of RTCM via Internet Protocol
ODD	Operational Design Domain
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
PKI	Public Key Infrastructure
PPP	Precise Point Positioning
RSU	Road Side Unit
RTCM	Radio Technical Commission for Maritime services
RTK	Real Time Kinematic
SBAS	Satellite-based Augmentation System
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
TTFF	Time To the First Fix
UE	User Equipment
V2I	Vehicle to Infrastructure
V2V	Vehicle to Vehicle
V2X	Vehicle to Everything
XiL	Everything in the Loop (Hardware and Software in the loop)
WAVE	Wireless Access in Vehicular Environments

Executive Summary

The objective of the deliverable

This deliverable presents the work done in HEADASTART work package 2: Task 2.2 “*Extension of current methodology for KETs¹*” and Task 2.3 “*Criteria for optimal scenario mapping according to tool and user group*”. T2.2 have identified a set of new parameters that should be included in the testing methodology described in D2.1 “*Common methodology for test, validation and certification*” when the HEADSTART enablers: positioning (with special focus on absolute positioning), communication (with special focus on Vehicle to Vehicle and Vehicle to Infrastructure communication) and cyber-security are introduced in the development of autonomous driving functions. Cyber-security is strongly connected to the positioning and communication since the GNSS satellite signals and the V2X messages are opening two new channels to cyber-attacks; it is important to identify a methodology able to verify the robustness of the system in all operating conditions. It should be noted that different KETs might have been identified but these three technologies are generally considered mandatory to reach SAE J3016 - Level 3 (and beyond) functionalities thanks to their capability to extend the vehicle perception, in space and time, together with the possibility to coordinates manoeuvres between the other vehicles and the road operator. In T2.3 have been identified the testing requirements that are necessary to perform a complete assessment of the Connected Autonomous Driving (CAD) system with special focus on the KETs: positioning, communication (V2X) and cyber-security. In current deliverable a revision of the four HEADSTART testing domains, described in D2.1: Proving Ground, Virtual Testing, X in the Loop and Real-world testing; have been performed to take in consideration the KETs specific needs. GNSS receivers and V2X communication modules have to rely on standardized protocols and messages therefore the proper behaviour of the CAD functions can be validated manipulating such inputs, even for black box systems, using simulators or signal generators able to recreate uncommon driving conditions or other rare events. Each testing methodology has its own advantages and weaknesses depending on the function or device under test but each of them are necessary to explore all the operative conditions of the driving system and to check the overall safety of the system when uncommon events occur.

¹ KETs: Key Enabling Technologies: Positioning, Communications (V2X), Cyber-security in HEADSTART project.

1 Introduction

1.1 The HEADSTART project in a nutshell

HEADSTART (Harmonised European Solutions for Testing Automated Road Transport) is a European project funded under Horizon 2020 Framework Programme within the call ART-01-2018 (the type: Research and Innovation action). HEADSTART is represented by the consortium of 17 partners that are top automotive manufacturers, suppliers, test labs and researcher institutes.

HEADSTART will define testing and validation procedures of Connected and Automated Driving (CAD) functions including:

- Its key enabling technologies (KET) (i.e. communication (v2x), cyber-security, positioning)
- Cross-links of all test instances such as simulation, proving grounds and real world field tests
- Safety and security performance validation according to the needs of key user groups (technology developers, consumer testing and type approval).

HEADSTART has 3 ACTION PILLARS mapped with end users of the project results:

- Testing and validation (development): e.g. OEMs,
- Assessment - Consumer testing: e.g. Euro NCAP
- Certification (type approval): e.g. Type approval authorities & Technical services

FIGURE 1: HEADSTART OBJECTIVES

The five objectives of the HEADSTART project comprise:

- OBJECTIVE 1: IDENTIFY - Create a dynamic catalogue of existing methods, procedures and tools for testing, validation and certification considering multi-stakeholder requirements.
- OBJECTIVE 2: HARMONISE - Harmonisation of existing testing and validation approaches taking into account other industries and domains.
- OBJECTIVE 3: DEFINE & DEVELOP - Define and develop test, validation and certification methodologies and procedures for CAD building upon existing initiatives.
- OBJECTIVE 4: DEMONSTRATE - Demonstrate the developed methodologies, procedures and tools through the testing of relevant CAD use cases.
- OBJECTIVE 5: REACH CONSENSUS - Reach consensus by creating and managing an expert network of CAD testing to promote adoption of the project results considering multi-stakeholder needs.

WP7 Coordination and management - The main objective is to ensure the successful execution of the project through a professional and effective management and coordination, with the achievement of the project objectives. WP7 contains all the technical and administration related project management and will deal with all Data Management related issues.

WP8 Ethics requirements - The objective is to ensure compliance with the 'ethics requirements' set out in this work package.

1.2 HEADSTART methodology

The HEADSTART testing methodology has been described in deliverable D2.1 [1]; here the focus is the impact the three KETs: Positioning, Communication V2x and Cyber-security will introduce in the system. Figure 2 shows the contribution of HEADSTART KETs to the overall methodology described in D2.1. The operative scenarios are derived from real-life experimentations; an analysis on the recorded data will be performed in order to validate the operative conditions of the vehicle functions under test. These conditions will be mapped and converted into new concrete scenarios as explained in D2.1. At this level the KETs parameters, or the specific anomalies to the normal KET behaviour, will be modelled and injected to the scenario (Point A of Figure 2). Some tests like the jamming attack requires the activation of external interferences some other can be modelled and simulated like the degradation of the absolute positioning due to the lack of GNSS signal. Four testing blocks have been identified: Proving ground testing, X in the loop, Virtual simulation and Field Test. Depending on the function, or the possible anomaly to be investigated, it will be more convenient to use one testing methodology in respect to the other: the reacquisition time of the GNSS receiver is something that should be monitored with Hardware in the loop testing (XiL block); some vehicle functions could be validated using virtual simulation tools: the speed profile adaptation due to the presence of Road Work message. In some situation it is simpler to verify the proper behaviour of an autonomous system in an operative field test especially for black-box systems; in such a case a scenario creation/monitoring block will be used to stimulate and verify the overall performances (see Figure 2 point B). As an example a “record and playback” attack can be easily performed when a trusted vehicle is available during the test (more details on record and playback attack will be provided in Section 2.2.2).

FIGURE 2 IMPACT OF KETS IN THE OVERALL HEADSTART METHODOLOGY

1.3 Structure of the deliverable

The deliverable is composed by two main chapters: in Section 2 the additional parameters that should be taken into account when positioning for safety purposes (Section 2.1) are reported, communication for cooperative driving (Section 2.2) and cyber-security (Section 2.3) are included into the validation methodology. The three KETs are not independent therefore references between parameters are explicitly reported. In Section 3 an extension to the methodology identified in D2.1 for the allocation of scenarios is presented. The same four testing procedures have been analysed and integrated to take into account the new parameters: Proving ground testing (Section 3.2), Virtual testing / simulation (Section 3.3), X in the Loop – XiL (Section 3.4) and Real world testing on open road (Section 3.5). Final remarks are presented in Section 4.

2 Identification of Positioning, Communications (V2X) and Cyber-Security parameters

A general description of the requirements for these KETs have been presented in D1.3 [2] and D1.4 [3]; in this section are reported the parameters that should be taken into consideration in the testing procedure when the Positioning, Communications (V2X) and Cyber-security enabling technologies are included into the design of safety vehicle functions. The introduction of these technologies for safety is quite recent therefore standardized procedure have not been already identified by the car makers or the suppliers. In T2.2 “*Extension of current methodology for KETs*” sixteen new parameters have been identified, starting from the user-needs identified in D1.3 (chapter 3.1). Figure 3 shows the list of the parameters: it should be noted that interdependences exist between the three selected KETs, all the connections have been highlighted in Figure 3 with a specific marker: Positioning (1), Communication V2X (2), Cyber-security (3).

A description of all the parameters is provided throughout Section 2. The main objective is to explain why the parameter must be taken into account, the operative context and the expected/acceptable reaction of the system under test. In some cases multiple causes could affect the same parameter; these parameters are described individually in the report because the validation procedure might vary significantly. For each element the following categories are reported:

Test Case: description of the parameter and how it will affect the performance of the system.

Measurement Unit: how to measure the parameter variation.

Testing Requirements: how the system should be tested in order to experience the problem.

Expected behaviour during the test: expected and/or acceptable reaction of the system to the anomaly.

FIGURE 3 ADDITIONAL PARAMETERS INTRODUCED BY HEADSTART KETS: POSITIONING, COMMUNICATION AND CYBER-SECURITY.

2.1 Positioning: GNSS and CAD (Road ITS)

2.1.1 Introduction

The availability of the absolute positioning system enables the vehicle to match its own position with map data and therefore to use road information beyond the reach of car sensors: the presence of obstacles on the driving path, as well as dangerous variations on the road geometry, or unexpected manoeuvres performed by other vehicles. The most convenient way to evaluate the vehicle position is the use of the Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS) thanks to the global availability and the reduced cost of the user equipment². The performances of the system until 5 years ago was only sufficient to enable satellite navigation but recently some GNSS manufactures have created devices able to reach lane level accuracy fulfilling the automotive constraints in terms of automotive specifications (HW robustness and ASIL-B SW certification) and mass production availability. Thanks to these performances the GNSS receiver could be used as an additional input information for the ADAS and Autonomous Driving systems. It must be said that it is difficult to rely only in one sensor due to the variety of the hazardous situation that may appear on the road. The position calculation of a driving function usually is performed via sensor fusion, being the GNSS the one providing the absolute position. Several solutions are emerging from different suppliers but a common, standardized methodology is not available yet. The positioning will play a crucial role in SAE-L3 onwards since the vehicle is the responsible of the driving function.

- Absolute position is required;
- Precise positioning since the driving function requires to drive within a lane;
- Integrity is required to ensure the performance.

In this chapter we have identified the parameters, which should be taken into account, in a GNSS assisted vehicle, in order to evaluate the reliability of the solution. Refer to Positioning node of Figure 3 to match each item to the relevant parameter and to check the interrelations with other two KETS.

2.1.2 Parameter description

1. Time To First Fix

Test Case: the Time To the First Fix (TTFF) is a measure of the time required for a GNSS receiver to acquire: the satellite signals, the navigation data and calculate the position solution (called a fix). The first fix will take more time than a re-acquisition because the GNSS system needs to recover the information on the orbits of all the GNSS satellites before computing its own position based on trilateration. There are three stages: Cold start: no information is available at the receiver and therefore the receiver entails a full search of the sky for all satellites; Warm start: the receiver has a valid almanac (either stored from a navigation message recently decoded or obtained via other means like Assisted GNSS). Furthermore, a rough position is also needed together with approximate information on frequency offset; Hot start: the receiver has both accurate ephemeris and information on frequency offset as well as an accurate initial solution.

Measurement Unit: time [s].

Testing Requirements: the TTFF strongly depends on the solution type: single positioning, SBAS (Satellite Based Augmentation System) systems are characterized by roughly 30 seconds, which can

² In theory other absolute positioning solutions can be exploited: triangulation based on traffic signs placed in known position, triangulation based on cellular-tower signals. But the benefit of GNSS solution overwhelms all the alternatives in terms of availability, reliability and performances. In practice the other channels will be used as backup solution in case of failures of the GNSS system.

be reduced with Assisted GNSS technique, RTK (Real Time Kinematic) is characterized by timing ranging from 30 to 120 seconds, PPP could take up to several minutes before to converge to a sub-meter solution. It should be noted that no map-matching is possible when absolute positioning is not available.

Expected behaviour during the test: the tester should verify how much time is necessary to perform the Fix in Cold start conditions. The system is in Cold start condition when the following conditions are met: Time unknown, current almanac (how many satellites are operative) and ephemeris (the parameters of each satellite orbit) are unknown, a rough estimation of the receiver is not available. This information is generally lost when the device is turned off for more than 4 hours. Forcing a cold start, for testing the system with a GNSS simulator for instance, might be not straightforward because it could open the systems to spoofing attacks (further information on this in the following parameters).

2. Reacquisition time (temporary lack of GNSS Fix)

2.1. Few second unavailability

Test Case: Vehicles frequently drive below bridges, overpasses or pylons especially in the motorways. The width of this obstacles is typically in the order of several meters (<20 m). In these conditions the LoS components of almost all the GNSS signals will be loss (even if for a few seconds).

Measurement Unit: time [s].

Testing Requirements: the positioning module should fuse the information coming from the car sensors, in addition to the GNSS receiver. In such a way that even in case of temporary loss of the GNSS signals the performance can still rely on relative positioning input. The most popular sensors in the automotive sector are: wheel odometers, IMU (combination of three axis accelerometers, gyroscopes, pitch/roll sensors and sometimes magnetometers), camera (lane and traffic sign detection).

High definition GNSS receiver (like the RTK solution) are more sensible to the loss of the LoS components. In particular several seconds could be necessary to recover the fix after the loss of the GNSS signals.

Expected behaviour during the test: the first task of the tester is understanding if the positioning solution relies on a pure GNSS solution or if other sensors are involved in the positioning module. The most convenient way to understand this is to drive toward a long tunnel or underground parking area. If the tester has access to the GNSS antenna it is not necessary to drive in a location where real bridge are present, they could be simulated with GNSS generators or building RF switches that disconnect the antenna when necessary. The output of the positioning module is not always available from black box systems but the tester can check what the outcome from warning messages or anomalies in the driving function.

If the positioning module is based on GNSS pure solution: the ego vehicle should be not able to retrieve updated information when no Fix is available.

If the positioning module is based on data fusion between GNSS and other sensor: the demonstrator should be tested in proving ground/real life test to identify how it reacts to the lack of GNSS data.

2.2. Persistent unavailability

Test Case: GNSS signal cannot be guaranteed for the entire trip. In motorways the reason for persistence unavailability is the presence of tunnels (the lengths could last from hundred meters to several kilometres). In the urban environment GNSS signals the main reason for persistent unavailability of GNSS fix is are the underground parking areas; in all the other

driving conditions the GNSS signals are less stable current GNSS systems are able to evaluate the vehicle position.

Measurement Unit: time [s].

Testing Requirements: the positioning module should rely on other sensor to continue to work properly. Dead-reckoning together with map-matching is the easiest solution. In case of long tunnels the camera is essential to allow the vehicle to maintain lane keeping control.

Expected behaviour during the test: similarly to previous case the positioning module react in a different way if the positioning module is based on GNSS pure solution the ego vehicle or if a data-fusion algorithm has been developed. In the first case the system is not able to retrieve updated information from the HD maps when no Fix is available. If positioning module is based on data fusion GNSS plus other sensors: the demonstrator should be tested in proving ground/real life test to identify how it reacts to the lack of GNSS data. As before it is not necessary to drive in a location where tunnels are present to experience the lack of GNSS data: it can be simulated with GNSS generators or building RF switches that disconnect the antenna when necessary. The main difference between few seconds of GNSS unavailability and a persistent loss is the time required from the system to recover a high quality fix and the major impact of sensor drift for inertial sensors.

2.3. Interference (Jamming)

Test Case: the GNSS signals have to travel 20.000km before reaching the vehicle; this implies the received signal is weak and can easily be overwhelmed from electronics close to the user. When a user intentionally creates an interferences in the GNSS bandwidth the cyber-attack is called “Jamming”. The main consequence of a GNSS jamming, or GNSS interference in general, is the loss of the GNSS fix. Identifying the cause of a missing fix due to interferences is not trivial; specific equipment with directional antenna is generally required. Jamming events are currently rare events, but their impact could create big issues when safety applications will rely on the GNSS data only.

Measurement Unit: time [s].

Testing Requirements: the positioning module should be able to identify when GNSS performances are unstable or insufficient to perform a reliable fix. In general Integrity algorithms and Protection Levels should be implemented. See point 4.1 of the Positioning parameters.

Expected behaviour during the test: interferences (intentional or not) are usually affecting GNSS receivers of vehicles driving in a specific area. Jamming is most likely to occur in urban areas for two reasons: 1. many sources of interferences are present, 2. vehicles are driving in smaller areas therefore they are in the coverage of jamming source for more time in respect to the highway scenario. Robustness to interference should be validated with jammers controlled by the operator. Some specific attacks can be performed by GNSS generators still it is difficult to predict the propagation of an RF interference in the real world.

3. Position offset (2D-3D)

3.1. Multipath effect

Test Case: the multipath effect is created by building, trees and other big elements. In the case that the LoS signal is not available the GNSS receiver cannot compensate the additional delay introduced by the reflected signals. This phenomena creates incorrect position fix with several meters of error. Multipath error is the dominant factor in urban scenarios while it is usually negligible in the motorways.

Measurement Unit: coordinate offset: [deg] or [m].

Testing Requirements: the increasing number of GNSS satellites and frequencies should reduce the impact of multipath. In addition to that, some suppliers are proposing some solutions able to identify and mitigate the multipath phenomena: 1. identification of sudden modifications of the signal, 2. Integration of 3D maps to check if the LoS is hindered by the buildings, 3. Coherency of the vehicle dynamics with other sensors. The multipath detection/mitigation algorithms are innovative topics for the automotive positioning therefore are usually protected by patents and the details not available to the tester.

Expected behaviour during the test: the vehicle should be tested in a well know environment in order to evaluate its resistance against multipath events. Multipath effect can also be simulated with GNSS simulators still the anti-multipath algorithms typically rely on inertial data therefore for black boxes system it is (typically) necessary to validate the positioning module is necessary to recreate consistency between inertial data and GNSS simulation.

3.2. Few satellites in view

Test Case: The quality of the GNSS fix strictly depend on the number of satellites available to triangulate the position. In general the following criteria can be used to assess the positioning module based on GNSS pure solution:

- $x < 3$: no 3D absolute position can be evaluated; 2D positioning is still possible with errors in the order of hundreds of meters.
- $3 < x < 8$: poor performances - Solution unstable; 3D positioning is possible but with typical GNSS errors > 10 meters.
- > 8 : good sky conditions; stable 3D positioning.

Measurement Unit: coordinate offset: [deg] or [m].

Testing Requirements: even if 3D positioning is technically possible with just 4 GNSS satellites in reality the performances will improve, in terms of accuracy and stability, increasing the number of satellites. The more satellites we have the better it is. With the exploitation of the full operational capability of 4 global constellations (GPS, GLONASS, GALILEO, BEIDOU) it is possible to achieve good GNSS fix everywhere in the world, including hopefully dense urban areas. The parameter measuring the quality of the fix is called Dilution of Precision (DoP). It shall be noticed that GNSS augmentation services and corrections data can heavily impact on the accuracy of the solution still the stability of the system will always be impacted by the total number of satellites that can be used to evaluate the position.

Expected behaviour during the test: the tester should be in position to compare the performances of the localization system monitoring the total number of satellites used by the GNSS engine to perform the fix. GNSS simulator can be used to check the performances of the device under test when a limited number of satellites are in view. In the case the device under test has integrated inertial sensors it could be necessary to physically obstruct the sky visibility or to test the system with a moving car.

3.3. Wrong vehicle path due to Spoofing attack

Test Case: spoofing is cyber-attack hackers can perform to let the GNSS receiver believe that the user is driving on a different trajectory in respect to the real one. Spoofing attacks can be very simple like: record & playback of a real GNSS source or very sophisticated, a totally new GNSS constellation identical and geosynchronous to the real world signal.

Testing Requirements: different strategies can be adopted to identify and reject a spoofing attack: in some cases is possible to identify the direction of arrival (DoA) of the attack, in other

cases a plausibility check is performed from the system. In general the safest way to identify a spoofing attack is by comparison of the vehicle dynamics between the GNSS trajectories and inertial sensors. Reliable positioning modules can be achieved only when data fusion algorithms are implemented: inertial sensors, camera and radar validation but also communication (e.g. V2I, V2V).

Measurement Unit: coordinate offset: [deg] or [m].

Expected behaviour during the test: data fusion algorithms create, in general, problems in the assessment of GNSS based localization system because they will identify anomalies when the tester is trying to replicate a GNSS anomaly experienced during a trial. The tester should verify if the positioning system will provide erroneous path when a fake GNSS signal is injected to the GNSS receiver. This can be performed with GNSS generator mounted inside the vehicle. System relying only on GNSS pure solution will be hacked even without moving the vehicle while the ones with data-fusion algorithm could detect the attack (and stop generating the absolute position) or provide wrong output.

4. Clock offset

4.1. Wrong time in the vehicle due to spoofing attack

Test Case: GNSS signals carries very accurate time information thanks to the atomic clock mounted on the satellites. This is the most reliable, economic solution, available at global level, to retrieve accurate time inside the vehicle. This is particularly relevant when the information of the car should be synchronized with external actors (other vehicles or infrastructure). In-vehicle application can typically synchronize their clock with hundreds of microsecond's precision. A spoofing attack (similarly to a GNSS simulator) could set an incorrect absolute time to the vehicle creating problems into the system relying on time-synchronized information.

Measurement Unit: time shift [s].

Testing Requirements: understanding how difficult is to force a date & time change into the vehicle is important. The absolute time is part of V2X communication module where time information should be typically synchronized with time accuracy lower than 1[ms]. Other systems of the car can also be affected by an incorrect time: SW modules can be disabled due to certificate outage or wrong navigation plan could be displayed to the driver.

Expected behaviour during the test: the vehicle can retrieve the proper time information from several channel: GNSS signals, NTP servers, radio broadcast. Still the easiest way to retrieve the absolute time with accuracy lower than 1 [ms] is the GNSS solution. Tricking the vehicle time from GNSS means to perform a spoofing attack. The tester should check if the system relies only on GNSS channel trying to modify the other source of time information.

5. Relative positioning offset

5.1. Lateral positioning offset due to lack of lane markings

Test Case: the best way to detect a lane change is to monitor the lane marking on the roads. This is the classical approach to develop SAE level 2[2] functionalities like: Lane centring and Lane Keeping assists applications. If the lane marking are missing the function is generally switched off. For autonomous SAE level beyond 2, camera recognition will still be one of the mandatory sensors therefore monitoring what happen when lane markings information is not available is important.

Measurement Unit: lateral shift [m].

Testing Requirements: the tester should investigate the behaviour of the ADAS/AD function in presence and absence of lane marking information. Lane marking information could be not available for several reasons: the road does not have lane marking painted on the asphalt, there are obstacles hindering the lane markings, adverse weather conditions or dirt present in front of the camera. Understanding what will happen in all these circumstances is critical to validate and assess the AD function.

Expected behaviour during the test: the performances of the systems can be very different depending on architectural choices: the function could be simply disabled in SAE L2 vehicles but for greater it is expected the vehicle to perform safe stop manoeuvre or continue to safely driving until the driver recover the control of the car.

6. Position error boundaries

6.1. Error boundaries identified by day-to-day repeatability

Test Case: GNSS system is designed to be time independent. The positioning errors should be caused by the internal noise of the GNSS receivers or other environmental anomalies: multipath reflections, unpredictable delay due to scintillations or tropospheric propagation or the presence of obstacles hindering the GNSS LoS signal. The GNSS repeatability is important to figure out the variation of the outputs driving in the same environmental at different time of the day. The performances of the system could be significantly different depending on the testing areas and the GNSS solution (single positioning, SBAS, PPP, RTK).

Measurement Unit: coordinate offset: [deg] or [m].

Testing Requirements: the ideal positioning system should return the same output every time the test is performed: regardless the time of testing or any other environment condition. This could occur in case map-matching algorithms are implemented, still the GNSS pure solution will be subjected to errors that should be identified and classified. Three GNSS classes have been identified by ETSI TS 103 246 standard [4]: Class A, Class B and Class C. Note this classification has been made for generic navigation devices without taking explicitly into account the automotive needs.

Expected behaviour during the test: check the stability of the system repeating the test in different days in the same location. GNSS simulators/generators can help to the system in the very same sky conditions: navigation model, almanac, clock deviations, ionospheric and tropospheric models. Three critical scenarios have been identified by ETSI TS 103 246 standard [4]: Open Area, Urban Area, and Asymmetric Area.

6.2. Error boundaries identified by to age of the correction data

Test Case: some ADAS and AD functions require sub-meter positioning: to achieve such performances GNSS correction data is mandatory. Correction data tells the GNSS receiver how to compensate propagation errors. Correction data are characterized by a geographical and time validity. They should be continuously sent to the GNSS receiver, if communication link is broken, the performances will be degraded together with the age of the correction. The geographical distance as well as the time validity depend on the type of GNSS solution: SBAS - continental coverage, several minutes' validity, RTK – some kilometres validity, seconds validity.

Measurement Unit: coordinate offset: [deg] or [m].

Testing Requirements: correction data should be available continuously. In general it is retrieved from satellite link channel for SBAS system and via cellular network (via NTRIP protocol) for RTK and PPP based solutions. Note that real time sub-meter performances,

enabled by GNSS positioning, can be achieved only with RTK and PPP solutions. For the RTK and PPP correction data the automotive functions usually relies on car maker private network (or their suppliers); this implies that, in general is not possible to inject the RTK corrections of simulated GNSS signal to the vehicle without the specific consent of the car maker. This also means that the most advanced AD black box solutions should be tested in real life conditions.

Expected behaviour during the test: the tester should assess how the performances will be degraded with the age of the corrections. Even if GNSS corrections cannot be easily injected to the positioning system (due to OEM private communication channel) it is usually easier to block the cellular connectivity. A lack of GNSS corrections for more than one minute will usually result with positioning error greater than one meter. This time could be significantly longer if data-fusion algorithms are implemented in the car. In some architecture the corrections can be retrieved via satellite-link; in this condition the corrections will be, in general, available all the time.³

In principle the GNSS corrections have limited geographical validity but in reality the vehicles can drive everywhere therefore the car-makers (or the correction provide) will always provide GNSS corrections for very wide areas (UE, North America, Asia, etc...).

7. Protection levels availability

Test Case: the protection levels bounds the position error with a confidence level derived from the integrity risk requirement. Where the integrity risk is the measure of the trust that can be placed in the correctness of the GNSS output. In other words: protection levels guarantee the positioning error is always less than the quantity identified by the positioning system.

An automotive standard to define protection levels is currently missing but several suppliers are proposing their own integrity algorithms based on the solution available for the aviation. The system should be able to identify that the position evaluated by the positioning system is within the declared error (with probability of errors $<10^{-5}$).

Measurement Unit: % of error in the error evaluation.

Testing Requirements: the tester should check how many times the positioning systems provide an incorrect positioning output within predefined protection levels. The objective is to understand if the positioning system is able to detect an erroneous output. A trade-off will occur between reliability of the solution and accuracy of the positioning solution. Big protection areas will provide great confidence of the solution but protection areas bigger than one meters will be also useless for an autonomous driving system. It should be noted that protection levels and integrity algorithm cannot be developed without data-fusion between GNSS data and other inertial sensors.

Expected behaviour during the test: the positioning module should be tested in different environmental conditions to check how the system react in all the possible driving scenarios. The temporary lack of GNSS signals (like tunnels or small bridges) are particularly relevant because will expose how much the positioning system relies on the GNSS satellites to provide reliable output. The testers should create a ground-truth or an alternative reference system to compare the output generated by the positioning system.

³ GNSS corrections via satellite link are usually distributed with geostationary satellites therefore the signals is not available in location at very high latitudes.

2.2 Communication (V2X)

2.2.1 Introduction

In the overall parameter table, there are various phenomena (or effects) that influence communication (V2X) behaviour. Some scoping decisions for the parameter table are:

- The parameters and corresponding tests are collected for behaviour and performance on (single) vehicle level. Normally component and unit level testing is already done by suppliers, this is a well-established practice and standardised and can be reflected through documentation from safety assessment. The need for innovative testing is in the area of full vehicle testing. Possible system levels to distinct are: unit/component level, function level, application level, single vehicle, multi-vehicles (system-of-vehicles)
- The detail of analysis and testing of interest is from system level and higher levels. Underlying phenomena like bit loss or jamming will result in V2X message loss. From a vehicle function and behaviour level, this is the relevant effect to be tested. If low level errors or faults do not end up in a V2X message loss through repetition or self-correcting mechanisms, they only lead to a V2X message delay, which should be taken into account as a phenomenon.
- For communications (V2X) some parameters relate to different underlying phenomena, or can originate from different communication layers, but still will have the same effect at CAD application level.
- More complex cooperative application are not bounded to a single vehicle level but consist of multiple vehicles, or a system-of-systems, with complex interactions enabled by communications (V2X). An example of such a CAD application is (Truck) Platooning.

2.2.2 Parameter descriptions

8. No usable V2X messages:

A V2X station should drop some messages for several reasons: to protect the system from cyber-attacks or to avoid crashes or malfunctions due to interoperability problems. The V2X standard foreseen several mechanisms to reject: messages coming from un-authorized stations, messages corrupted in the air, delayed copies of valid messages. The basic concept valid for ITS applications (both IEEE802.11p and PC5⁴) standards is based on digital signature with certificates generated by a common authority, see ETSI TS 102 940 [5] for Europe and IEEE1609.2 [6] for US. The list of the parameters to be included into the validation is reported below. It should be noted these parameters are strongly connected with Cyber-security, as depicted in Figure 3.

8.1. Untrusted V2X source

Test Case: an attacker could generate V2X messages from an unauthorized Root Authority. The V2X station is supposed to verify the signature of all the V2X messages. All the stations participating to the V2X must subscribe themselves to the a common Public Key Infrastructure (PKI) in order to retrieve certificates and a Certificate Revocation List (CRL) to validate if the received messages have been transmitted by an authorized station. Therefore, communication must be established only with trusted sources and only permit the traffic of trust messages.

Measurement Unit: [-] Activate cyber-attack/anomaly.

Testing Requirements: the tester should use V2X generators to create valid V2X messages signed with pseudonyms coming from a different Root-CA in respect to the official one. It should be noted

⁴ PC5: direct communication channel for Cellular V2X (C-V2X) according to 3GPP Rel. 14/15 and Rel. 16 devices

that an official common PKI is still not available. The OEMs that are running V2X services are using private PKIs.

Expected behaviour during the test: if the V2X messages are not signed, or fail the verification process, the communication module has to drop the V2X messages. In some cases the messages must be dropped because the PKI has inserted the transmitting station into the CRL. In the case the attacker was able to retrieve a valid certificate, the V2X station should perform a plausibility check in order to identify unrealistic behaviour, possibly supported by redundant communication channel.

8.2. Digital signature missing from V2X messages

Test Case: the test is very similar to the previous parameter with the difference that in this case the message does not contain the security header. The lack of secure communication layer will expose the vehicle to man-in-the-middle attack, because there is no way to check if the messages have been manipulated by un-authorized users.

Measurement Unit: [-] Activate cyber-attack/anomaly.

Testing Requirements: The tester should generate messages without the security layer activated according to the standard ETSI TS 103 097 [7]. The ego vehicle should drop the messages because untrusted.

Expected behaviour during the test:

The V2X station should subscribed to an entrusted PKI and process messages that have passed the verification procedure. If messages are unsigned, the communication channel must be blocked. The vehicle will ignore the source of information.

8.3. V2X message is corrupted

Test Case: an attacker could modify one, or more, data elements of a messages transmitted from a trusted station with valid digital signature. The V2X standard foreseen a verification procedure that starting from the digest and the digital signature will detect the corruption.

Testing Requirements: an attacker should try to retransmit messages coming from trusted vehicles changing some of the elements such as the timestamp or the validity are of the message. The system should be able to detect the corruption.

Measurement Unit: [-] Activate cyber-attack/anomaly.

Expected behaviour during the test: as part of the security function the V2X message integrity should be verified. For security, use tamper-resistant protocols across communication links, data hashing and signing (digital signature). Corrupted messages should be dropped.

8.4. Delayed V2X messages: record & playback attack

Test Case: V2X messages are sent together with a digital signature in such a way that the receiver is in position to verify if the message has been modified from third party users. Record and playback attacks will not change the content of the message, it will create an authentic delayed replica therefore the message will pass the verification process. In order to avoid such problem all the V2X messages contain a timestamp which should be used to identify old/replayed messages. There is still the possibility to the attacker to pass the verification process: if the attacker is able to modify the system clock of the target vehicle. This is possible with a Spoofing attack (see Section 2.1.2: "Positioning parameter description: Clock Offset").

Measurement Unit: [-] Activate cyber-attack/anomaly.

Testing Requirements: the V2X receiver should implement the V2X security stack according to ETSI ITS-G5 Security Architecture [5]. This implies that all the messages should be verified. All the messages shall be dropped: without security shall be dropped, expired validity or with timestamp

set in the future, with invalid or untrusted authorization tickets, authorization tickets present in the Certificate Revocation List, type of messages generated by not-authorized station.

Expected behaviour during the test: two vehicles, the ego-vehicle and a remote vehicle able to communicate via V2X, are necessary to check the robustness of the ego-vehicle to a record and playback attack. The remote vehicle will start generating V2X messages. The tester will start recording the messages and will reproduce them with minimum delay. The ego-vehicle should detect the duplicate messages. The tester should check: if the ego-vehicle is able to discriminate the two messages and the maximum delay admitted by the ego-vehicle to drop the attacker messages. In case the tester is in condition to perform a Clock Offset attack (see Section 2.1.2: "Positioning parameter description: Clock Offset") the test should be repeated with the same hour recorded in the original message.

8.5. V2X message not trustworthy

Test Case: attackers get unwanted access to user equipment (UEs) without permission (e.g. repudiation, spoofing, and elevation of privilege attack.).

Measurement Unit: [-] Activate cyber-attack/anomaly.

Testing Requirements: the User Equipment (UE) should guarantee authorization for access.

Expected behaviour during the test: if communication module is based on V2X (e.g. IEEE 802-11p, 4G/LTE) pure solution, the vehicle should be able to detect unauthorized access to UEs. If unauthorized access is detected, security mechanisms will try to cancel communication. Alternatively, other valid communicating channels should be used to retrieve the information.

8.6. V2X communication logs (repudiation check)

Test Case: security mechanism should keep track of all the events occurring into the vehicle. If an attacker get access to the (communication) system without rights, i.e. successfully performing an elevation of privilege attack.

Measurement Unit: [-] Activate cyber-attack/anomaly.

Testing Requirements: the tester should try to access the communication module and grant the access to critical signals/data (as an example the CAN bus signals activating the braking system).

Expected behaviour during the test: the communication security function should detect and inform about issues regarding authentication and access control of the communication system. For this all the system access activities should be traced and recorded in a log file. A program should check the incidents and inform about unauthorized access. The vehicle will try to report it to an authorized agent (typically the OEM back-end service).

8.7. V2X message is not encrypted, validated and verified

Test Case: when system requirements require encrypted communication: all the messages must be encrypted by certificate validation (trusted certificates), and authentication (verified signatures) in accordance with the security solution implemented.

Measurement Unit: [-] Activate cyber-attack/anomaly.

Testing Requirements: the tester should try to corrupt the content of the messages or break the confidentiality.

Expected behaviour during the test: if encryption is required, the messages must be encrypted with a secure communication protocol with trusted certificates and verified signatures to authenticate. The communication security function must block untrusted messages and verify communication protocols. The vehicle must reject communication with communication channels

that do not meet these requirements and try to establish a new communication fulfilling the security protocol.

8.8. Virus (or new S/W) is embedded in V2X embedded on-board equipment:

Test Case: a virus/malware (or new S/W) is embedded on the communication to user equipment or vehicle telematics system.

Measurement Unit: [-] Activate cyber-attack/anomaly.

Testing Requirements: the attacker should try to corrupt the SW or firmware of the V2X system. In case of success it should be estimated the impact on the vehicle functions. The system could detect the anomaly and disable the AD functions or the attack could not affect any relevant component.

Expected behaviour during the test: security check should be performed to ensure the integrity of the SW. Check if virus is embedded or malicious code is injected, communication should prevent forwarding infected packets.

8.9. Interoperability issues

Test Case: V2X standard is still evolving: even if the message dictionary is quite stable there is still quite flexibility in the use of optional data frames, especially in the implementation of I2V services developed across different EU (or US) countries. The result is that vehicles could experience malfunctions due to different implementation of the V2X standard.

Measurement Unit: [-] Activate message with different data format.

Testing Requirements: the system should be tested against several V2X implementations in order to verify the interoperability of the system in all the countries where the vehicle are supposed to drive. In addition to the tester should generate V2X messages generated from older version of V2X standard or with unrealistic values.

Expected behaviour during the test: the vehicle function should be implemented in order to detect and ignore the content from V2X messages received with different/incorrect implementation. Check if improperly encoded messages will results in system failures.

9. Wrong timestamp:

This parameter is related to time synchronisation issues at local vehicle level and will directly impact the robustness of the CAD application. Time synchronisation between all on board vehicle systems is of great importance to successfully deploy a local CAD application. On top, cooperative services and applications need this to have an accurate and synchronised timing at vehicle level.

9.1. V2X message with outdated timestamp (positive or negative time lag)

Test Case: Robustness of the system to time synchronization issues (intentional or not). Since GNSS signal is commonly used to synchronize the system clock of the vehicle this parameter will impact all the HEADSTART KETs.

Measurement Unit: clock offset [s].

Testing Requirements: Timestamps are added to V2X messages and/or are part of the payload. This information can be used to drop messages with outdated time information. The active CAD application will set acceptable threshold values for the message delay.

Expected behaviour during the test: The actual CAD application threshold values that are practical, are mainly driven by the overall robustness of the application against message delays. The system should drop messages with outdated information (or information claiming to be in future when they have occurred in the past).

10. Latency:

This parameter is related to the time delay of the complete V2X message to get to its destination. Also this parameters can be addressed at multiple communication layers. Delay will be the overall effect at application level, with different underlying causes as detailed out in the following:

10.1. Increased latency due to effective coverage range

Test Case: the delay in the V2X reception is due to the loss of good communication link caused by communicating stations being out of radio coverage range. Before complete messages loss the Packet Error Rate (PER) will start to increase because messages will be lost due to low received signal strength. Since the V2X messages are usually periodic messages these losses will result in an increasing latency. The communication range can be severely impacted by the presence of obstacle hindering the LoS such as trucks or buildings.

Measurement Unit: delayed messages [ms].

Testing Requirements: Robustness of active CAD application will determine how much latency (due to retransmission) is acceptable, and how much packet loss (PER) is acceptable. The typical threshold defined for a good communication channel to trigger V2V warnings (i.e. threshold not defined for AD functions) is $PER \leq 10\%$ [8]. The tester should check the maximum communication range of the communication module in free space and urban conditions. The same parameters should be used in simulated environment to simulate the channel quality depending on the communication distance. Typical communication range between vehicles is 300[m]. Note: the test should be performed deactivating the congestion control algorithm of the vehicle or in an environment where very few V2X stations are transmitting. Check next parameter for more information on Congestion Control component.

Expected behaviour during the test: depending on the application the system should react differently. I2V services such as: presence of road-works ahead, don't require frequent updates while coordinated manoeuvres functions such as truck platooning are very sensible to latency and packet losses in general. The important point, no matter the application, is the capability of the vehicles to detect when the communication link is not stable enough to fulfil the requirement of a specific application.

10.2. Increased latency due to message loss caused by Channel Congestion.

Test Case: the capability of the vehicles to communicate with other actors depends on two factors: Channel Busy Ratio (CBR) and the Packet Error Rate (PER). The V2X communication based on ETSI ITS-G5 is a Carrier-sense multiple access with collision avoidance (CSMA/CA) protocol; the V2X stations can transmit if the communication channel is not already in used by another station. If the channel is busy the station will try to retransmit the message as soon as the channel becomes free. In current protocol up to 1500 messages/s can be generated by the stations before reaching relevant latency in the communication.

PER is a measurement correlated to the packet loss; messages are lost if the power of the received messages is below the receiver sensitivity (usually -94dBm) or if interferences are strong enough to corrupt the V2X messages.

The V2X protocol foreseen a Congestion Control algorithm that limit the overall number of messages in the air based on the CBR and the PER evaluations. The main idea is that whether a unit detect a too high CBR and loss of messages it will start decreasing the frequency and the transmitting power of its own messages. In such a way the channel will be occupied for less time and at smaller distances.

Measurement Unit: delayed messages [ms].

Testing Requirements: the V2X system should be able to identify that channel congestion is occurring and performed the decongestion control procedure to reduce the overall V2X burden according to the V2X specifications [9]. Usually channel congestion will start to become relevant when over 100 vehicles are present in the same area, therefore it is very unlikely to experience congestion problem during plug-fest, testing pilots or proving ground testing activities.

Expected behaviour during the test: the tester should use V2X message generators to simulate a crowded scenario. The system should start reducing the emitting frequency and power of the V2X messages. Congestion control algorithm must be implemented to reduce the collapse of the V2X network.

On the other side the robustness of the application to this type of event must be tested; the maximum acceptable latency is application dependent, therefore it is important to check what happen to the system without transmitting some of V2X messages (message decimation).

10.3. End-to-end latency (minimum time from trigger to reception)

Test Case: One important quality parameter for receiving road safety applications is the knowledge of the "age" of data to enable the application to interpolate the received data values for a situation evaluation corresponding as close as possible to the real originating vehicle situation, e.g. trajectory, velocity. Consequently, whatever the application is considered, the quality of the offered customer service will be relying on the quality of available data at the receiving ITS-S level. The age of data at the receiving level is then depending on the distributed application end to end latency time for critical road safety application (collision avoidance) and for pre-crash application an estimated 300[ms] end to end [10]. Different latency might be applied for coordinated manoeuvres or the most advanced AD functions.

Measurement Unit: minimum delay [ms].

Testing Requirements: the tester should check the amount of time required by the systems from the generation of a specific event to the generation of the vehicle reaction: a warning on the cluster or a corrective manoeuvre by the AD system. CAD applications using these messages should comply with the time application requirements and this will set the minimal acceptable timing boundaries (at vehicle level, between vehicles, between vehicle and infrastructure).

Expected behaviour during the test: for certain ITS application definitions timing requirements can apply, additionally for the use of ITS messages. Example in case of event triggered events the V2X message should be generated and received from the other vehicle with end-to-end latency time boundaries (example < 300[ms] for Road Hazard Signalling [10]. It is crucial the vehicle is able to identify outdated messages in order to guarantee the safety of the vehicle.

11. V2X messages out-of-order

Test Case: V2X messages can reach the remote vehicles with improper order, this could happen for several reasons: an attacker could try to record and playback messages, reflections could introduce delays to some messages or multi-hop propagation mechanism could create delayed copies of the V2X messages.

Measurement Unit: [-] message switch.

Testing Requirements: the tester should use V2X generators with out-of-order messages and check the reaction of the ego-vehicle functions.

Expected behaviour during the test: the system should be able to identify out of order messages and remove outdated information. The effect of out-of-order messages depends on the active CAD application (type of application, robustness of application, V2X protocols used). The system should be able to identify out-of-order messages and process them (drop or re-order them).

12. V2X network reliability

Test Case: this parameter relates to the communication availability (at vehicle level, between multiple vehicles) and the failure rate at CAD application level. It also relates to the Packet Delivery ratio: at vehicle level, between multiple vehicles and/or other communicating stations (I2V).

Measurement Unit: [-] message losses.

Testing Requirements: V2X message losses will degrade application performance. Testing relates to the robustness of the application against V2X network unavailability, for example caused by local (environmental) conditions or of a temporal nature.

Expected behaviour during the test: The effect of V2X message loss depends of the active CAD application (type of application, robustness of application). The application can detect V2X message loss and act accordingly (log, alarm, automated response, degraded mode).

13. Denial of Service:

13.1. Denial of Service of the communication channel by blocking due to interference (jamming)

Test Case: this is an intentional interference on the communication channel performed by an attacker to deny the communication signal to reach the vehicle. The result is the impossibility to process any data coming from the other V2X stations.

Measurement Unit: [-] Activate cyber-attack/anomaly.

Testing Requirements: the V2X communication module doesn't receive incoming messages. Using data from other sensors, from its communication module, or via another approach the vehicle should detect the attack.

Expected behaviour during the test: the communication (V2X) module is not able to receive information from other vehicles/users. In some cases the V2X module could be able to identify the source of an interference and nullify it with directional antenna.

13.2. Overflow of communication channel with fake data

Test Case: burst of fake data on the V2X channel can result in an overload of the V2X receiver capacity, and/or the internal vehicle communication system. Note that the verification procedure is very demanding process in terms of computational power therefore it might happen to saturate the systems resource in the operation. If the attacker is able to perform an attack able to saturate the channel bandwidth the result will be the activation of the Congestion control algorithm as described in the paragraph 10.2 "Increased latency due to channel congestion". In this case the attack can be classified as Denial of Service attack on the communication channel. Overloading the internal system will start introducing message delays and or messages losses and could also result in a complete Denial of Service.

Measurement Unit: [-] Activate cyber-attack/anomaly.

Testing Requirements: the tester should try to generate burst of V2X data in presence of other genuine V2X messages. The objective is to check if the ego-vehicle can still operate properly.

Expected behaviour during the test: a successful attack will make the communication channel unstable or unusable for the ego-vehicle or the entire network. The vehicles should identify the problem and remove the V2X channel from the inputs supporting the CAD functions.

2.3 Cyber-Security

2.3.1 Introduction

Before the allocation of scenarios in the different possible tests, KETs formed by positioning, communication and cybersecurity introduce different scenario parameters to enhance the final concrete scenario. The extension of these scenario parameters provides a better understanding of the future possible testing scenarios and introduce KETs in the scenarios as a relevant technology to improve the comprehension of the environment.

Cybersecurity is the practice of protecting systems, networks, and programs from cyberattacks. Implementing effective cybersecurity measures is particularly important for safety and security of smart cars. Automated or autonomous vehicles can be objectives of attacks that can lead to traffic accidents, vehicle damage, killed or severe injured road users, disclosure of confidential personal data and even financial losses. All such attacks that threat security, safety and even privacy of vehicle passengers, must be mitigated by implementing appropriate security measures.

Appropriate security measures require a set of appropriate technical controls, policies and procedures and processes to mitigate the attack risk. In order to achieve such security measures, deliverable 1.4 [3] provides common practices and standards to be followed (see Chapter 2.1.3 “Requirements on testability of the KETs – Cybersecurity” in the deliverable 1.4). The application of common practices and standards shall draw the attention of companies for responsible and careful handling when developing vehicles and preventing cyber-attacks. Within the different activities of the entire lifecycle of vehicle systems, the concept and product development phase activities define the design of the system, generating, as a result, the cybersecurity concept, refined cybersecurity specification, cybersecurity requirements for post-development, verification report for the refined cybersecurity specification, vulnerability analysis report, integration and verification specification and reports, documentation of the modelling, design or programming languages and coding guidelines, and software unit design and software unit implementation (based on ISO 21434 [11]). Among all the activities, functional and technical cybersecurity requirements are the most relevant ones.

Deliverable 1.3 [2] presents compiled requirement for KETs from a HEADSTART perspective (see Chapter 4 “Compiled functional and technical requirements for KETs” in the deliverable 1.3). The compiled requirements are used to provide a framework for focusing on obtaining the scenario parameters. To improve the final concrete scenario, cybersecurity provides a set of different scenario parameters listed and classified together with the other KETs.

Finally, some scoping decisions for the scenario parameters are:

- As the communication section (chapter 3.2), the parameters and corresponding tests are collected for behaviour and performance on vehicle level. It is assumed that the system-level tests are already performed by the suppliers, following a well-established and standardized practice, and can be reflected through the safety and security assessment documentation. However, it is necessary to connect the tests at the vehicle level to system level part and generate a complete traceability on the test results.
- Cybersecurity address parameters in a multi-layer communication and positioning models. For example, analysing vulnerabilities in the v2x communication based on the wireless access in vehicular environments (WAVE) from the IEEE 802.11p standard.

2.3.2 Parameter descriptions

The parameters from the overall table related to both positioning and cybersecurity are reported in this subsection (see more details in section 3.1.2. “Parameter descriptions” for details on the parameter section)

2. Reacquisition Time (lack of GNSS fix)

2.3 Interference (Jamming)

3. Position offset (2D-3D)

3.3 Wrong vehicle path due to Spoofing attack

4. **Clock offset:** wrong time in the vehicle due to Spoofing attack

The parameters from the overall table related to both communication and cybersecurity are reported in this sub-section (see more details in section 3.2.2. "Parameter descriptions" for details on the parameter section)

8. No usable V2X messages

8.1. Untrusted V2X source (fake messages)

8.2. V2X message is not trustworthy

8.3. V2X communication logs (Repudiation check)

8.4. Digital signature missing or performed from an untrusted PKI.

8.5. V2X message is not encrypted, validated and verified

8.6. V2X message is corrupted

8.7. V2X message is delayed: record & playback attack

8.8. **Virus (or new S/W) is embedded in V2X embedded on-board equipment**

Special mention is required for the description of this parameter: the property refers more to cybersecurity than communication (V2X) function. Properties such as integrity, availability and confidentiality have special attention to cover cybersecurity requirements in that specific environment parameters. However, such cybersecurity parameters are needed to be part intrinsic of communication existing a clear dependence between them. Therefore, that group of parameters are addressed in section 2.2.2. "Communications (V2X) - Parameter descriptions".

14. Denial of Service

14.1. Denial of Service (blocking due to interference).

14.2. Communication overflow with fake data

The parameters from the overall table related to privacy and cybersecurity are described and explained in this sub-section.

15. Certificate Rotations

Test Case: an attacker could use the digital signature of a vehicle to track the movements of the driver. To avoid privacy violation, the vehicles have several certificates that will expire every two weeks; in addition to that the vehicle will use 20 certificates that should rotate periodically. A description of the certificate rotation procedure is described in [8]. Briefly two conditions should be met to perform a certificate rotation: 5 minutes have passed, and the vehicle has driven a distance greater than 2[km].

Measurement Unit: [-] Certificate switch event.

Testing Requirements: the tester should monitor the certificates generated by the V2X system and verify the certification rotation procedure met the requirements of the V2X standard.

Expected behaviour during the test: the V2X vehicles are supposed to rotate their certificates periodically. After two weeks new certificates should be used. The number of certificate the vehicles

should store is limited (usually one year certificates are provided) therefore the V2X module should periodically subscribe to the PKI to retrieve or update the certificates.

16. SW package updates

16.1. Legitimate updates not applied

Test Case: S/W updates cannot be applied on several V2X parts.

Measurement Unit: [-] system fault.

Testing Requirements: each S/W package lying through the communication process should be able to be updated from legitimate sources.

Expected behaviour during the test: legitimate FW update process fails or is not considered legitimate after an attempt. If update process has an available update that is legit FW, the previous updated system should inform the failure and wait till receive the confirmation to a second try update.

16.2. Illegitimate updates applied:

Test Case: Illegitimate S/W updates applied on several V2X parts.

Measurement Unit: [-] system fault.

Testing Requirements: the tester should try to perform an update with illegitimate FW. In case of detection, a roll-back process should be applied to the previous well-functioning version. Each S/W package lying through the communication process should be able to be updated from legitimate sources.

Expected behaviour during the test: if an update process fails or is not considered legitimate after an attempt, a roll-back process should be applied to the previous well-functioning version.

16.3. Misconfiguration or unintentional deletion of communication SW part(s)

Test Case: unintentional deletion/misconfiguration of SW packages affecting the proper V2X communication chain.

Measurement Unit: [-] system fault.

Testing Requirements: the tester should identify misconfiguration attempt and ensure roll-back capability.

Expected behaviour during the test: if SW package is misconfigured the system should be able to load default configurations. A notification message should be brought to the user attention with a tell-tale lamp or to the OEMs via an alternative channel.

3 Testing requirements for testing - KETs

This part reflects the work carried on in task 2.3 “Criteria for optimal scenario mapping according to tool and user group”. The main goal of this task was to setup a method for the allocation of scenarios to the test methods targeted by HEADSTART:

- Proving ground testing (test track)
- Virtual testing / simulation
- X in the Loop (XiL)
- Real world testing on open road

The method to allocate general driving scenarios was detailed in the deliverable 2.1. This chapter aims to extend this methodology to the three KETs targeted by HEADSTART (Positioning, Communication V2X, and Cyber-security) and detail the specificities and requirements for testing KETs on each test method.

3.1 General requirements

The parameters described in section 2 have an impact on the “robustness” of the application and they typically impose a non-functional requirement to the CAD system or application. It should be noted that different phenomena can have the same effect at the application layer. A good example is the parameter latency, which will impact the CAD application with a certain delay, but the source of the delay can be at all kinds of different layer such as: the environment, the physical layer, media related, network related, transport protocol related. This knowledge of the cause is very important as this will set boundaries and requirements, on what and how to test the function as part of the four types of testing used within HEADSTART: proving ground testing, virtual, XiL-based and real world.

In addition, some general remarks related to the identified parameters and for the overall HEADSTART assessment architecture:

- a) The enabling technologies Positioning, Communication (V2X) and Cyber-security are added at a single point in the HEADSTART architecture. To extend this assessment chain with Communication (V2X), probably the extension needs to be deployed at multiple points of the architecture for realistic CAD assessment.
- b) The enabling technologies are often not independent. Security functions for Communication (V2X) are often required, especially as TRL-levels grow. Additionally, privacy issues related to the V2V data is of interest and concern.
- c) The idea is to use a generic approach for the enabling technologies extensions for CAD assessment. In practice there will be a trade-off between generic and more application-specific approach to have useful assessments as CAD applications can differ much. For example, a cooperative application (e.g. Platooning) will need specific interactions between vehicles (system-of-vehicles), test use cases and V2X message exchange. Platooning vehicle interactions are depending of the information exchanged via V2X communications (input and output functions).

The above add layers of complexity for the assessment of these types of applications and will have an impact on how generic the CAD assessment approach can be, compared to single vehicle and non-cooperative applications.

From a communication (V2X) perspective some extra requirements are derived for the overall HEADSTART methodology. These are listed in the table below.

TABLE 1 ADDITIONAL REQUIREMENT FROM COMMUNICATION (V2X)

ID	Object	Requirement	Type	Comments
1	Field data	All incoming and outgoing V2V and V2I messages, and other relevant related information is logged.	Logging	And sensor information and driver actions, presumably in other requirements.
2	Field data	Based on classifying the V2X data as being tactical data or operational data different timing requirements apply. The information relevance (single destination, multiple destination) can differ.		This is often (platooning) application specific.
3	Accident data	Accident data includes the V2V and V2I communication from 20s before and after the incident	Logging	See 1)
4	Simulator studies	Simulation includes multiple vehicles and test V2V message exchange at logic level (protocol interactions)		This is application specific (example testing the interaction between platooning vehicles)
5	Scenario database	A scenario shall contain incoming V2X messages.	Scenario	May contain the message definition. For platooning is not standardised yet.
6	Scenario database	In the case of platooning, a scenario shall specify the vehicle role in a platoon.	Scenario	This can be (platooning) application specific
7	Virtual Simulation Testing	For simulating a scenario with two-way communication, the simulator shall have at least two interacting actors, engaged in communication.	Simulator	cooperative, highly coupled interaction, operational data (real-time)
8	Scenario database	In case of platooning, the scenarios are meant for testing an individual vehicle in the platoon.		As a platoon is a system-of-vehicles.
9	Proving ground testing	In case of platooning, physical tests will include multiple vehicles for platooning scenario testing.	Physical test	
10	Scenario database	The scenario database shall contain scenarios with a range of communication delays.	Scenario	
11	Scenario database	The scenario database shall contain scenarios with V2X message loss (message, package, frame)	Scenario	

Some of the listed requirements are specific for a system-of-vehicles like in the case of a platooning application. This is very relevant as (EU project) ENSEMBLE Truck Platooning is a selected use case for HEADSTART.

3.2 Proving ground testing

In the previous deliverable D2.1: “Common methodology for test, validation and certification”, we have addressed the general requirements that should be met in order to proceed Proving Testing for CAD systems. Proving Ground testing is a crucial part for assessment as it covers situations that could not be applied with only simulation (for example due to simulation SW tools limitation). And on the other hand, Open Road testing is also

somehow limited to restricted number of situations that can be encountered, there is also additional risk for human involved and for the vehicle under test. But the methodology that has been described in the D2.1 address specificities and testing items for general ADS without any distinction to a specific KET. The goal of this sub-chapter is then to add specific requirements to address technological specific items (KET): Positioning, Communication (V2X) and Cybersecurity that has not been addressed by the first deliverable.

The organization of the subchapter 3.2 will be as followed:

- The first paragraph (3.2.1) will replace the testing requirements in the general methodology of HEADSTART
- The test requirements relevant for the KETs selected for the HEADSTART project are described in the following paragraphs (3.2.2, 3.2.3, 3.2.4)
- The last paragraph will give a practical example of a testing requirement allocated to “Proving Ground” testing (0)

In the previous Chapter 2, we made a focus on the specific parameters that are expected to influence the behaviour of the CAD and the specific KETs. In this chapter, we will focus on testing requirements that shall be met in order to correctly test the specific parameters accordingly to previous chapter. More specifically, in this sub-chapter we will deal with specific requirements allocated for proving ground testing.

3.2.1 Generalities

Replaced in the general methodology, we would remind that test requirements are placed in the “Testing” part of the process. And more particularly, it is an input for “Allocation of Scenarios” and an output of the type of test (Virtual Simulation / XiL / Proving Ground). Hereafter, the general methodology extracted from D2.1 with a specific highlight (in red) that is addressed by this chapter.

FIGURE 4 TESTING REQUIREMENTS REPLACED IN THE GLOBAL METHODOLOGY

In order to have a common format for describing the testing requirements, it has been created a unique template for testing requirements. A testing requirement is composed of:

- **Requirement Id (Req #):** this field contains a unique identification number that help to identify and ensure traceability of the requirement. (e.g. : 43)
- **Category:** this field contains the information to know to which KET this requirement shall apply. (Positioning / Communication (V2X) or Cybersecurity)
- **Domain:** this field contains the information to know to which type of test (Proving Ground / Virtual Testing / XiL) the related requirement shall apply.
- **Subcategory:** this field contains the information to know to which sub-category the related requirement shall be allocated. For instance, this sub-category can contain a sub-module of the KET that would be particularly tested in the related requirement. Sub category can also mention an additional module specially used for this test requirement (e.g. : GNSS Generator)
- **Requirements:** This field contains an explicit description of all conditions and provisions that shall be met for the test to be feasible.

Category	Domain	Sub category	Requirements
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FIGURE 5 ENTRIES FOR THE TEST REQUIREMENTS MATRIX

The choice for this chapter is to divide the list of requirements in subchapter by grouping them by KET. The first sub-chapter will contain positioning dedicated test requirements, the second sub-chapter for Communications requirements and the third for cybersecurity sub-chapters.

3.2.2 Positioning

TABLE 2 TESTING REQUIREMENTS - PROVING GROUND: POSITIONING

Req #	Category	Domain	Sub category	Requirements
29	Positioning	Proving Ground	Reference GNSS	Use High precision GNSS survey grade receiver (RTK system usually) to check the positioning system of the DuT. Data fusion with IMU could be mandatory in case tunnels/bridges are present in the testing area. WGS84 performances should be lower than 10[cm].
30	Positioning	Proving Ground	GNSS corrections	GNSS reference station or NTRIP correction service should be provided to enable ground truth with centimeter level accuracy.
31	Positioning	Proving Ground	GNSS blockage	GNSS antenna should be accessible during the test. The antenna should be physically disconnected (or hindered) during the test to check the performance of the positioning system in case of lack of GNSS signal.
32	Positioning	Proving Ground	GNSS-OBU	Coherence between DuT and GNSS reference OBU: time and WGS84 position.
33	Positioning	Proving Ground	GNSS-OBU	Tunnels, Bridges or Urban environment should be available to stimulate the integrity/protection levels of the GNSS positioning system.
34	Positioning	Proving Ground	GNSS recorder	Record the GNSS signals for playback replication (laboratory testing).
35	Positioning	Proving Ground	GNSS	Injection of an offset on GNSS Latitude estimation on Virtual Testing Platform (x ° during y sec) (require open interfaces)
36	Positioning	Proving Ground	GNSS	Injection of an offset on GNSS Longitude estimation on Virtual Testing Platform (x ° during y sec) (require open interfaces)
37	Positioning	Proving Ground	GNSS	Injection of an offset on GNSS Heading estimation on Virtual Testing Platform (x ° during y sec) (require open interfaces)
38	Positioning	Proving Ground	IMU	If applicable, Injection of an offset on VUT longitudinal (x -axis) acceleration estimation (x m/s ² during y sec) (require open interfaces)
39	Positioning	Proving Ground	IMU	If applicable, Injection of an offset on VUT lateral (y -axis) acceleration estimation (x m/s ² during y sec) (require open interfaces)
40	Positioning	Proving Ground	IMU	If applicable, Injection of an offset on VUT vertical (z -axis) acceleration estimation (x m/s ² during y sec) (require open interfaces)

41	Positioning	Proving Ground	IMU	If applicable, Injection of an offset on VUT roll-rate (x-axis) estimation (x rad/s during y sec) (require open interfaces)
42	Positioning	Proving Ground	IMU	If applicable, Injection of an offset on VUT pitch-rate (y-axis) estimation (x rad/s during y sec) (require open interfaces)
43	Positioning	Proving Ground	IMU	If applicable, Injection of an offset on VUT yaw-rate (z-axis) estimation (x rad/s during y sec) (require open interfaces)
44	Positioning	Proving Ground	LIDAR	If applicable, obstruction of each LIDAR sensor (one by one) used for positioning purposes (during x sec)
45	Positioning	Proving Ground	LIDAR	If applicable, obstruction of all LIDAR sensors used for positioning purposes (during x sec)
46	Positioning	Proving Ground	Camera	If applicable, obstruction of each Camera sensor (one by one) used for positioning purposes (during x sec)
47	Positioning	Proving Ground	Camera	If applicable, obstruction of all Camera sensors used for positioning purposes (during x sec)

3.2.3 Communication (V2X)

TABLE 3 TESTING REQUIREMENTS - PROVING GROUND: COMMUNICATION (V2X)

Req #	Category	Domain	Sub category	Requirements
73	V2X	Proving Ground	V2X-RSU	Interoperability of V2X messages: ETSI ITS-G5/DSRC or PC5: messages coming from the DuT should be properly decoded by the RSU.
74	V2X	Proving Ground	V2X-RSU	Channel performances: Packet Error Rate (PER) vs Distances. The communication is reliable when PER<10%. Minimum Line of Sight (LoS) is 300m.
75	V2X	Proving Ground	V2X-RSU	DuT time synchronization: timestamp error should be lower than 100ms.
76	V2X	Proving Ground	V2X-RSU	Measurement of communication latency: from message generation until message reception in the RSU. Latency should be lower than 100ms.
77	V2X	Proving Ground	V2X-OBU	Coherence between DuT trajectory and V2X-OBU messages: WGS84 position, curvature and path history.
78	V2X	Proving Ground	V2X-OBU	Classification of remote objects (depending on distance and driving directions).
79	V2X	Proving Ground	V2X-OBU	Latency time from the trigger of a specific event/periodic message and the reception of a notification/warning into the DuT. End to end latency should be lower than 300ms.
80	V2X	Proving Ground	Other	Possibility to test the complete CAD vehicle system involving all Communication (V2X) layers. To test with systems-of-vehicles and with multiple communicating vehicles or infrastructure (I2V). This can often be considered an optimized environment with sometimes non-realistic environments for Communication (V2X) when compared to a real-world deployment (interference, obstacles, Non-LOS conditions).

3.2.4 Cyber-security

TABLE 4 TESTING REQUIREMENTS - PROVING GROUND: CYBER-SECURITY

Req #	Category	Domain	Sub category	Requirements
89	Cyber	Proving Ground	GNSS jammer	GNSS generator (to be connected close/directly) to the GNSS receiver to evaluate the performances of the positioning system.

90	Cyber	Proving Ground	V2X jammer	Overflow communication channel with fake data.
91	Cyber	Proving Ground	V2X jammer	V2X generator able to generate fake vehicles around the DuT.

3.2.5 Example of testing requirement allocated to “Proving Ground” testing

In order to illustrate the concept that has been described during the previous sub chapter, we will take an example of requirement and practically describe how this can be achieved and tested using Proving Ground Testing.

Let assume that the KET under test is a Positioning System:

FIGURE 6 EXAMPLE ARCHITECTURE OF POSITIONING SYSTEM

A typical positioning system may have several sensor inputs such as: vehicle odometers, GNSS, IMU, Camera and LiDAR.

A typical positioning system generally has one output which is an estimation of the Vehicle Pose in global reference frame (longitude, latitude and heading). This output Vehicle Pose estimation is then used to feed ADS such e-Horizon extraction or Lane Extraction on Cartography for Lateral Control.

Replaced in our global testing method, the testing requirements Req-ID35 to Req-ID37 would actually apply to this module brick as illustrated followed:

FIGURE 7 INJECTION OF LONGITUDE, LATITUDE, HEADING OFFSET ON GNSS INPUTS (REQ-ID35 TO REQ-ID37)

The data for GNSS sensor would be degraded by injecting estimation bias (Δx) for a given duration (Δt). This misestimating will then lead to a degradation on vehicle pose estimation and, consequently, an unintended behaviour at vehicle level. For example, if Positioning is used for maintaining the Automated Driving System onto its EGO-lane then a bad Vehicle Pose estimation will lead to degraded ability of the ADS to maintain his EGO-lane.

3.3 Virtual testing

The general methodology of HEADSTART project was introduced in the deliverable D2.1 as the outcome of the T2.1 Methodology and procedure description for CAD testing and validation. The following figure shows the functional diagram of the proposed methodology covering from data generation up to the diverse testing and evaluation.

FIGURE 8 OVERVIEW OF THE GENERAL METHODOLOGY OF HEADSTART (FROM: D2.1)

The extension of the current methodology to cover and include the HEADSTART selected KETs implies some variations in the overall Virtual Simulation Testing.

3.3.1 Data Format

The testing and validation require scenario description as has been addressed in D2.1 however, the current data formats and description languages cover only up to the manoeuvre descriptions based on movable objects. The following figure shows the data requirements in terms of complexity layers to describe a complete scenario including the data link to the KETs, especially to those describing the communication (V2X), the positioning and the cybersecurity.

<p>Layer 6: Digital information e.g. V2X communication, Connectivity</p>	
<p>Layer 5: Environment e.g. Weather, lighting and other surrounding conditions</p>	
<p>Layer 4.b: Other objects e.g. Dynamic and static objects</p>	
<p>Layer 4.a: Ego vehicle e.g. Dynamics and behavioural data</p>	
<p>Layer 3: Temporary manipulation of layer 1 & 2 e.g. Geometry, overlaid topology, time frame</p>	
<p>Layer 2: Traffic infrastructure e.g. Structural boundaries, traffic signs, elevated barriers</p>	

FIGURE 9 SCENARIO DESCRIPTION FORMAT: BASED ON PEGASUS 6 LAYER APPROACH AND MOOVE SCENARIO FORMAT

There are different approaches to describe the elements of the different layer, especially until layer4 where there are road and scenario description languages. However, OpenScenario (layer 4) and OpenDrive (layer 1, 2, 3) descriptions language from the German project Pegasus are considered the fact standards that recently has been transferred to ASAM for its standardisation, evolution and maintenance. Thus, and for being compliant with the standards the two languages will be considered the main data format for the layers 1, 2, 3 and 4.

OpenSCENARIO is an open file format for the description of dynamic contents in driving simulation applications. The primary use-case of OpenSCENARIO is to describe complex, synchronized manoeuvres that involve multiple entities like vehicles, pedestrians and other traffic participants. The description of a manoeuvre may be based on driver actions (e.g. performing a lane change) or on trajectories (e.g. derived from a recorded driving manoeuvre). Other content, such as the description of the ego vehicle, driver appearance, pedestrians, traffic and environment conditions, is included in the standard as well.

Open Drive: OpenDRIVE® is an open file format for the logical description of road networks. It was developed and is being maintained by a team of simulation professionals with large support from the simulation industry.

However, the layers 5 and 6 are not covered by the open standards such as OpenScenario and OpenDrive.

The inclusion of the selected HEADSTART KETs requires the definition of layer 6 which requires to describe the cooperative communication channel, the GNSS base signalling for position and the cybersecurity. HEADSTART in the WP3 will deal with the description and proposal of a language and ontology for describing these elements that are also related to the elements described in the previous layers, e.g. the V2X messages will depend on the vehicles on the scene and its dynamics.

3.3.2 Overview of the process

The overall process to include the KETs on the general methodology presented in the previous section the methodology requires to deal with the description of the environment. This action will happen after the concrete

scenario has been selected from the general Scenario database and the specific parameter selection been done in the relevant scenario selection module. Then, the process to be followed is shown on the next figure.

FIGURE 10 INCLUSION OF KETs IN THE VIRTUAL SIMULATION PROCESS

The selected concrete scenario will be enriched with OpenENVIRONMENT data which parameters will be related to the specific elements on the scene. This general KET inclusion on a specific scenario then need to be created. In this case the module for scenario allocation means that specific KET configurations will be analysed for a concrete scenario. This parameter exploiting will make that a single concrete scenario (until layer 4/5) will be multiplied with specific scenarios including KET parameters. The KET parameters that will be analysed are the ones presented in the previous sections.

FIGURE 11 KETs INCLUSION INTO CONCRETE SCENARIOS

3.3.3 KETs Parameter List - Positioning

The following table shows the Positioning related parameters for virtual testing that should be defined in the Scenario layer 6 definition.

TABLE 5 TESTING REQUIREMENTS - VIRTUAL TESTING: POSITIONING

Req #	Category	Domain	Sub category	Requirements
48	Positioning	Virtual Testing	Intermittent GNSS blockage	Intermittent loss of the GNSS information from the system (simulation of small obstacle). Remove GNSS fix for 2s and restore it afterwards.
49	Positioning	Virtual Testing	GNSS loss	Long duration loss of the GNSS information (simulation of tunnels long 300 meters long). Remove GNSS fix for 30s.
50	Positioning	Virtual Testing	Position offset	Constant WGS84 offset in respect to East (or North). Positioning offset depend on the scenario and the DuT under investigation (50cm is a good candidate for CAD functions).
51	Positioning	Virtual Testing	Position degradation in presence of Protection Levels	Performances of the positioning system will be degraded due to obstacles of GNSS signals. Increasing degradation respecting the Protection Levels (starting from 10cm till 10m).
52	Positioning	Virtual Testing	Delay of corrections	Performances of the positioning system will be degraded due to delay in the provision of GNSS corrections (starting from 10cm till 1m).
53	Positioning	Virtual Testing	GNSS Receiver	Injection of an offset on GNSS Latitude estimation on Virtual Testing Platform (x° during y sec)
54	Positioning	Virtual Testing	GNSS Receiver	Injection of an offset on GNSS Longitude estimation on Virtual Testing Platform (x° during y sec)
55	Positioning	Virtual Testing	GNSS Receiver	Injection of an offset on GNSS Heading estimation on Virtual Testing Platform (x° during y sec)
56	Positioning	Virtual Testing	IMU or INS	If applicable, Injection of an offset on VUT longitudinal (x -axis) acceleration estimation (x m/s ² during y sec)
57	Positioning	Virtual Testing	IMU or INS	If applicable, Injection of an offset on VUT lateral (y -axis) acceleration estimation (x m/s ² during y sec)
58	Positioning	Virtual Testing	IMU or INS	If applicable, Injection of an offset on VUT vertical (z -axis) acceleration estimation (x m/s ² during y sec)

59	Positioning	Virtual Testing	IMU or INS	If applicable, Injection of an offset on VUT roll-rate (x -axis) estimation (x rad/s during y sec)
60	Positioning	Virtual Testing	IMU or INS	If applicable, Injection of an offset on VUT pitch-rate (y-axis) estimation (x rad/s during y sec)
61	Positioning	Virtual Testing	IMU or INS	If applicable, Injection of an offset on VUT yaw-rate (z -axis) estimation (x rad/s during y sec)
62	Positioning	Virtual Testing	LiDAR Sensor	If applicable, obstruction of each LIDAR sensor (one by one) used for positioning purposes (during x sec)
63	Positioning	Virtual Testing	LiDAR Sensor	If applicable, obstruction of all LIDAR sensors used for positioning purposes (during x sec)
64	Positioning	Virtual Testing	Camera Sensor	If applicable, obstruction of each Camera sensor (one by one) used for positioning purposes (during x sec)
65	Positioning	Virtual Testing	Camera Sensor	If applicable, obstruction of all Camera sensors used for positioning purposes (during x sec)

3.3.4 KETs Parameter List - Communication (V2X)

The following table shows the V2X Communications related parameters for virtual testing that should be defined in the Scenario layer 6 definition.

TABLE 6 TESTING REQUIREMENTS - VIRTUAL TESTING: COMMUNICATION (V2X)

Req #	Category	Domain	Sub category	Requirements
81	V2X	Virtual Testing	V2X-OBUE	Interoperability of V2X messages: ETSI ITS-G5/DSRC or PC5.
82	V2X	Virtual Testing	V2X-Generator	Create messages with wrong timestamp
83	V2X	Virtual Testing	V2X-Generator	Create out of order messages
84	V2X	Virtual Testing	Other	Logical testing of V2X message exchange
85	V2X	Virtual Testing	Other	Using none, simple or complex communication (V2X) models

3.3.5 KETs Parameter List – Cyber-security

No specific Cybersecurity related parameters for virtual testing were found.

TABLE 7 TESTING REQUIREMENTS - VIRTUAL TESTING: CYBER-SECURITY

Req #	Category	Domain	Sub category	Requirements
#	Cybersecurity	Virtual Testing	N.A.	N.A.

3.3.6 Virtual Simulation Tools

The inclusion of KET technology description into the Virtual Testing environment will require some specific features to emulate the KET technologies and their impacts to the simulated elements. There are different approaches to tackle these requirements and the simulation capabilities will be limited by the final use of the

virtual testing. The black-box approach will require the conversion of the KET parameters into specific actions in the used simulation elements whereas the grey/white-box would require the emulation of the KETs signals.

3.4 XiL-Based testing Scenarios

To include the HEADSTART KETs in the methodology of XiL based testing, it is necessary to expand the approach. Since XiL based testing is a combination of virtual elements and proving ground or Hardware in the Loop tests, the simulation of KETs becomes a key element. The definitions used for the description of KETs can be reused for any type of testing. There are three KETs, namely Positioning, Communication and Cyber-Security. Positioning is either based on communication or is based on other layers and therefore implicitly included in the scenario. On top of that, cyber-attacks are usually based on communication channels. Thus, the execution of tests on communication level is crucial for the testing of KETs. It can be challenging to test communication effects on the proving ground with real components, since the effects are very diverse. There is multi-path-propagation, shielding, reflection just to name a few when it comes to V2X. The effects are even more diverse, thus a complete testing is challenging. However, within the simulation it is easier to simulate the effects of the named problems. It is not feasible to place a wall or a building on proving grounds, but easy to implement in simulations. Thus, either the final effect like jitter, delay or replay can be tested with real components, but for a more detailed testing, scenarios need to be simulated when it comes to V2X. Thus, we propose the use of simulation-based testing of V2X components while keeping the rest of the XiL methodology from the original methodology.

3.4.1 Positioning

The following table shows the Positioning related parameters for XiL testing.

TABLE 8 TESTING REQUIREMENTS - XiL: POSITIONING

Req #	Category	Domain	Sub category	Requirements
66	Positioning	XiL	GNSS generator	Identification of Time To First Fix (TTFF). First genuine should be achieved within 30s.
67	Positioning	XiL	GNSS generator	Identification of position degradation in presence of GNSS blockage. Intermittent losses of GNSS signals (scenario where small bridges are present): block the GNSS signals for 2s and restore it afterwards.
68	Positioning	XiL	GNSS generator	Identification of position degradation in presence of GNSS blockage. Long duration losses of GNSS signals (scenario where tunnels are present): block the GNSS signals for 30s and restore it afterwards.
69	Positioning	XiL	GNSS generator	Identification of position degradation in presence of Multipath effect model: occasional insertion of GNSS multipath component.
70	Positioning	XiL	GNSS playback	Generate the GNSS signals as previously recorded. Verify anomalies of GNSS system.

3.4.2 Communication (V2X)

The following table shows the V2X Communications related parameters for XiL testing.

TABLE 9 TESTING REQUIREMENTS - XiL: COMMUNICATION (V2X)

Req #	Category	Domain	Sub category	Requirements
86	V2X	XiL	Conformance	Conformance testing to relevant standards. E.g. ETSI PlugTest events, or a similar approach (testing, tools, evaluation)
87	V2X	XiL	Interoperability	Interoperability testing to relevant Standards. E.g. ETSI PlugTest events, or a similar approach (testing, tools, evaluation)
88	V2X	XiL	Conformance	C-V2X conformance/compliance testing
89	V2X	XiL	Interoperability	V2X interaction testing, V2V, I2V, V2I interactions. CAD application specific tests: triggered response, messaging logic, interaction protocols (e.g. Platooning application)
90	V2X	XiL	Stress Testing	Generation of high message loads for the DuT, stress testing the V2X communication system (channel load, Rx buffers, message encoding/decoding, message filtering, application performance/robustness testing. (at Virtual Testing ,XiL, Proving Ground)
91	V2X	XiL	Other	Software in the Loop, Hardware in the Loop including V2X radio module or V2X communication units
92	V2X	XiL	Other	Simulation, emulation of network at Radio level / Network level / Transport level

3.4.3 Cyber-security

The following table shows the Cybersecurity related parameters for XiL testing.

TABLE 10 TESTING REQUIREMENTS - XiL: CYBER-SECURITY

Req #	Category	Domain	Sub category	Requirements
97	Cyber	XiL	Conformance	Conformance testing to relevant Cooperative-ITS security standards. E.g. ETSI Plug Test events, or a similar approach (testing, tools, evaluation)
98	Cyber	XiL	Interoperability	Interoperability testing to relevant Cooperative-ITS Security Standards. E.g. ETSI Plug Test events, or a similar approach (testing, tools, evaluation)
99	Cyber	XiL	Conformance	Testing CAD application performance/robustness/resilience against external attacks (V2X, wireless comm.) (Jamming V2X, DoS channel, DoS Tx/Rx V2X messaging, spoofing V2X messages etc.)

3.5 Real-world testing scenario

The real-world testing scenario offers the possibility to expose the system to an extremely wide variety of real conditions related to Operational Design Domain (ODD) that would not be feasible with proving grounds or simulations. In Section 2, there were listed a set of parameters that will influence one of each specific KETs. In this section it has been selected the ones which are strongly related to the open-world scenario.

3.5.1 Generalities

The open road testing needs to be executed under a framework that maintains traceability of results between Field-Operational-Tests, Proving Ground and Virtual testing. The figure below shows the functional overview of the methodology.

FIGURE 12 GENERAL METHODOLOGY FOR OPEN ROAD TESTING

Specifically, in this document it will be described the list of requirements that will be used for defining the scenarios after. It can be seen in Figure 12 marked in red. In order to fulfil these requirements, the connected autonomous vehicle shall be able to:

- **Determine location:** assuming that the connected autonomous vehicle feature is Geo-fenced, the system should be able to determine location, whether inside or outside, relative to the operational design domains (ODDs).
- **Perceive relevant static and dynamic objects:** all entities that an automated driving system needs to be aware of for its functional behavior should be perceived.
- **Detect unavailability due to performance degradation:** function unavailability due to degradation must be identified, including the reason.
- **Determine if specified nominal performance is not achieved:** factors such as unwanted human factors (misuse), deviation from the intended functionality, technological limitations, and environmental conditions influence nominal performance.
- **Correctly execute and actuate the driving plan:** driving plan should generate lateral and longitudinal control, based on driving plan and strategy.
- **Reduce system performance in the presence of failure for the degraded mode:** the reaction in case of failures during degraded mode should be tested.
- **Communicate and interact with other road users:** depending on the specific ODD, Automated driving vehicles could be required to communicate and interact with other road users.

3.5.2 Positioning testing requirements in Real World

TABLE 11 TESTING REQUIREMENTS - REAL WORLD: POSITIONING

Req. #	Category	Domain	Sub category	Requirements
1	Positioning	Real world	Camera	The camera should be able to perceive all relevant static and dynamic objects to be able to react accordingly.
2	Positioning	Real world	Camera	The system shall be able to detect the camera unavailability due to performance degradation including the reason.
3	Positioning	Real world	Failure	The system shall reduce the performance in the presence of GNSS failures during degraded mode.
4	Positioning	Real world	Failure	The system shall reduce the performance in the presence of sensors failures during degraded mode.
5	Positioning	Real world	GNSS-fix	The system shall be able to determine its own location, whether inside or outside using a high precision system (RTK).
6	Positioning	Real world	GNSS-fix	The system shall be able to drive below bridges, overpasses, pylons or long tunnels when there is a lack of GNSS fix. Fuse data from vehicle sensors available (IMU, camera...) shall be used when driving under these conditions.
7	Positioning	Real world	GNSS-fix	The system shall be able to drive in underground parking when there is a lack of GNSS fix. Fuse data from vehicle sensors available (IMU, camera...) shall be used when driving under these conditions.
8	Positioning	Real world	GNSS-fix	The system shall be able to detect and correct the position error and produce a position fix with fusion of other sensors or other correction signals when is driving in a zone with buildings or trees.
9	Positioning	Real world	GNSS-fix	The GNSS service shall use information from at least 8 satellites to perform correctly. If the GNSS is using information from 3 to 7 satellites, fuse data from other sensors shall be used.
10	Positioning	Real world	GNSS-OBU	The specified nominal performance is not achieved due to human factors (misuse), deviation from the intended functionality, technological limitations or environmental conditions.
11	Positioning	Real world	GNSS-Robustness	The robustness to interference shall be guaranteed with jammers controlled by the operator, especially when driving in urban areas.
12	Positioning	Real world	GNSS-Routing	The system shall be able to correctly execute and actuate the driving plan generating lateral and longitudinal control based on the strategy.
13	Positioning	Real world	GNSS-signal	When the GNSS signal cannot be guaranteed for the entire trip (presence of long tunnels, parking...), the system shall rely in fuse data from vehicle sensors available.
14	Positioning	Real world	LIDAR	The LIDAR should be able to perceive all relevant static and dynamic objects to be able to react accordingly.
15	Positioning	Real world	LIDAR	The system shall be able to detect the LIDAR unavailability due to performance degradation including the reason.
16	Positioning	Real world	Radar	The Radar should be able to perceive all relevant static and dynamic objects to be able to react accordingly.
17	Positioning	Real world	Radar	The system shall be able to detect the Radar unavailability due to performance degradation including the reason.
18	Positioning	Real world	Regulation and exemptions	Instrumented vehicles or functions under test need to acquire the necessary exemptions to be used in open roads
19	Positioning	Real world	Route selection	The system shall be able to identify the suitable route specific to test the target driving function.
20	Positioning	Real world	Route selection	The system shall be able to detect the presence or density of elements (perception blockers, VRUs density...) before the route selection.
21	Positioning	Real world	Route services	HD map services shall be available for accurate localization functions.
22	Positioning	Real world	Route services	SD maps shall be available for navigation services.

3.5.3 Communication (V2X) testing requirements in Real World

The main topics of requirements on V2X communication for real world testing are the Infrastructure requirements (e.g. availability of communication base stations, signal receivers, V2I credentials...).

TABLE 12 TESTING REQUIREMENTS - REAL WORLD: COMMUNICATION (V2X)

Req. #	Category	Domain	Sub category	Requirements
23	V2X	Real World	V2X-RSU	The V2X device (e.g. vehicle) shall be able to discover and/or directly communicate to nearby devices with relevant characteristics and information and receive data.
24	V2X	Real World	V2X-RSU	The V2X device (e.g. vehicle) shall be able to receive data at maximum frequency and range.
25	V2X	Real World	V2X-RSU	The V2X device (e.g. vehicle) shall be able to send data at maximum frequency and range
26	V2X	Real World	Interoperability	The ITS-G5 device shall be able to send and receive CAM messages in realistic situations, such as dynamic frequencies and required communication range, and in static and mobile situations.
27	V2X	Real World	Interoperability	The ITS-G5 device shall be able to send and receive CAM and other messages, such as DENM, SPAT, MAP, in realistic situations, such as dynamic frequencies and required communication range, and in static and mobile situations.
28	V2X	Real World	Interoperability	The V2X device shall be able to send and receive data in realistic situations, such as dynamic frequencies and required communication range, and in static and mobile situations, and node density.
29	V2X	Real World	V2X-degradation	The system shall be able to detect the V2X unavailability due to performance degradation including the reason.
30	V2X	Real World	V2X-RSU	Latency from message generation until message reception in the RSU. Latency should be lower than 100ms.

3.5.4 Cyber-security testing requirements in Real World

No specific requirements for cybersecurity on open road testing were found.

TABLE 13 TESTING REQUIREMENTS - REAL WORLD: CYBER-SECURITY

Req. #	Category	Domain	Sub category	Requirements
31	Cybersecurity	Real World	N.A.	N.A.

4 Conclusion

New technologies are emerging to support the most advanced autonomous driving assistance systems, from SAE J3016 L3 and beyond: absolute positioning, cooperative vehicles (V2X communication) and an in-vehicle cybersecurity framework. These systems enable to extend the vehicle perception, in space and time, together with the possibility to coordinate manoeuvres between other vehicles and the road operator. Nevertheless, these technologies rely on information coming from sensors outside the design domain of the car makers. The deliverable has presented the implications that these new technologies, called Key Enabling Technologies (KETs) in HEADSTART, are bringing into the development and the validation procedure of safety functions. Sixteen new parameters have been included to the testing methodology described in D2.1. For each parameter the information necessary to understand the risk associated to the specific KET and the expected behaviour of the overall system in all the operative conditions has been provided. An update on the testing blocks described in D2.1: Proving Ground, Virtual Testing, X in the Loop and Real world testing, has been reported as well. The systems using the HEADSTART KETs will require specific tests in order to assure the proper operability in all the driving circumstances. The outcome of: T2.1 *“Methodology and procedure description for CAD testing and validation”*, which results are reported in D2.1 *“Common methodology for test, validation and certification”*, T2.2 *“Extension of current methodology for KETs”*, which results are reported in current deliverable and T2.3 *“Criteria for optimal scenario mapping according to tool and user group⁵”*, which results are reported in both D2.1 and the current deliverable, will be used as starting point for the definition of a complete testing methodology on selected HEADSTART use cases by T2.4 *“Definition of methodology for the targeted use cases”*.

⁵ User group aspects have been detailed in D2.1, chapter 5.3 *“Mapping and user group needs”*.

5 References

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